

How to consider feasibility aspects of transformation pathways for the industry sector - implications for energy systems modelling

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ABSTRACT

The practical feasibility of GHG mitigation pathways is increasingly acknowledged as essential to climate scenario development. However, energy system models (ESMs) still lack a structured and comprehensive approach for integrating feasibility considerations. This study proposes a conceptual framework that addresses this gap by guiding the integration of feasibility aspects into model-based scenario studies, with a specific focus on the industrial sector.

At the heart of the proposed concept lies the Feasibility Loop—the core contribution of this work. It provides a structured, visual, and process-oriented approach to systematically link existing methods, indicators, and data sources across the entire modelling process. The loop identifies key steps in a model-supported feasibility assessment, clarifies how different types of methods contribute to these steps, and supports modellers in understanding where and how feasibility aspects can be meaningfully integrated.

The framework is built around three distinct types of feasibility constraints—hard, quantitative soft, and qualitative soft—which serve as a conceptual bridge between assessment content, modelling tools, and interdisciplinary knowledge. Supporting components include a 5W1H-based structuring of the research context, a typology of feasibility-relevant indicator categories, and guidance for modelling requirements such as granularity and adaptability.

Rather than prescribing a fixed workflow, the proposed concept serves as a flexible toolbox, enabling tailored application depending on available resources and research goals. Finally, it aims to improve the relevance, comparability, and transparency of scenario results and support more robust decision-making in the transformation of energy-intensive industry systems.

Abbreviations

AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
CIB	Cross-Impact Balance (Analysis)
CPC	Central Product Classification
ESM	Energy Systems Model

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GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IAM	Integrated Assessment Model
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISIC	International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities

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(continued)

MCDM	Multi-Criteria Decision Making
MDE	Multi-Dimensional Evaluation
MGA	Modeling to Generate Alternatives
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal (analysis framework)
RDM	Robust Decision Making
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

1. Introduction

Achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement requires both ambitious targets and the effective implementation of deep decarbonisation pathways. Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) [1] formalise national ambitions, yet global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the industrial sector continue to rise [2]. One reason for this may be a persistent discrepancy between model-based, mostly normative scenarios and real-world implementation—especially in the industrial sector, where complexity, actor diversity, and structural constraints pose a particular challenge to the feasibility of emission mitigation.

Despite its central role in global emissions, the transformation of the industrial sector is underrepresented in feasibility assessments. Notably, the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) evaluates feasibility in most sectors but lacks such analysis in the industry chapter [2]. This appears to be a significant research gap, given the sector’s heterogeneity: as shown in Fig. 1, industrial subsectors differ significantly in energy demand [3], CO₂ emissions [4], and process temperatures [5]. These characteristics impact the technical and practical viability of mitigation options, underscoring the need for context-specific approaches.

Industrial associations across the globe have published transformation roadmaps in recent years, reflecting growing awareness and commitment [6–11]. These roadmaps address practical barriers to implementation that can significantly affect the feasibility of mitigation pathways. However, such real-world constraints are still rarely reflected in scientific and policy-oriented scenario studies, which often prioritise techno-economic optimisation while overlooking feasibility factors critical for actual implementation.

Energy systems models (ESMs) and Integrated Assessment Models

(IAMs) are key tools in developing long-term bottom-up-based transformation pathways. Yet feasibility is typically addressed only after scenario generation, if at all. In this article the authors explore the possibilities for change from the perspective of practitioners of scenario-based studies. We follow the argumentation that this narrow treatment is inadequate (see Section 2.2) and feasibility concerns should be integrated into the entire modelling process—from the design phase of the study to interpretation and communication. With this in mind, the article pursues the following objectives:

- To offer practical and broadly applicable approaches to systematically embed feasibility considerations into industrial decarbonisation scenario studies;
- To emphasise that feasibility encompasses more than economic viability, including institutional, social, environmental, and technological dimensions;
- To theoretically show how feasibility assessments can be meaningfully integrated throughout the modelling process.

Rather than proposing an entirely new theoretical framework, this study presents a comprehensive and practice-oriented concept based on current literature and developed from the perspective of experienced modellers. It illustrates how feasibility concerns can be systematically addressed across the full modelling workflow.

At the heart of this concept is the Feasibility Loop—a visual and procedural guide that links established methods and modelling practices into a coherent, iterative process. The loop helps modellers identify which feasibility aspects matter in a given context, which methods can be applied, and at what stage of the process. It serves as a flexible structure to operationalise feasibility without prescribing a one-size-fits-all approach.

To guide our analysis, we pose the following research questions.

1. What are the conceptual and methodological core requirements for systematically representing feasibility considerations within scenario-based mitigation studies for the industry sector?
2. How can existing methods and modelling practices be aligned within a structured process to enable feasibility-oriented scenario design?
3. What conclusions can be drawn from the modelling practice in current NDC studies regarding the integration of feasibility aspects, and

Fig. 1. Industry subsectors according to the International Standard Industrial Classification of all Economic Activities (ISIC) with statistical data on global final energy consumption [3] and GHG emissions [4] of 2019 and temperature levels of process heat [5] to illustrate the heterogeneity of the industry sector.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the literature research conducted in this study and meta data for all studies considered.

what actions are needed to advance their consideration in industrial decarbonisation studies?

To answer these questions, we draw on a synthesis of literature, sector-specific modelling experience, and insights from the NDC Aspects research project [12]. We identify core theoretical requirements and assess how they align with current modelling practices. Our study suggests that feasibility-relevant information can be generated and evaluated more effectively—using existing tools and models—if guided by a structured concept such as the Feasibility Loop.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the theoretical foundations and state of the art in feasibility assessments. Section 3 describes the methodological approach. Section 4 presents the results, including the Feasibility Loop and associated model requirements. Section 5 provides a critical discussion, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Theory on feasibility considerations in energy systems modelling

As a first step, we reviewed the existing literature to understand how feasibility is currently defined, assessed, and addressed in decarbonisation pathways and energy systems modelling, with the goal of identifying key requirements and gaps relevant for the systematic integration of feasibility into industrial scenario studies.

2.1. Method used for the literature review

A simplified systematic literature review was conducted in 2024 and 2025, the process of which is illustrated in Fig. 2 as a flow diagram. To ensure a broad and inclusive evidence base, comprehensive search criteria were applied to titles, abstracts, and keywords within leading citation databases, including Scopus,¹ Semantic Scholar,² and Google Scholar.³ The review focused on peer-reviewed publications and comprised six distinct search queries across the three databases. Each query combined relevant keywords using Boolean operators (AND, OR), and for each, the top 50 entries ranked by relevance were screened. Following a two-stage screening process, this initial search yielded 27 relevant publications. Although no restriction was placed on the year of publication during the search, the final selection of studies spans the period from 2014 to 2025. This database-driven review was subsequently supplemented through Artificial intelligence-assisted literature discovery using the online tool ResearchRabbit.⁴ By uploading the 27 initially identified studies, an additional seven relevant sources were found. Furthermore, the review was expanded to include 32 additional

¹ Weblink: <https://www.scopus.com>.

² Weblink: <https://www.semanticscholar.org>.

³ Weblink: <https://scholar.google.com>.

⁴ Weblink: <https://www.researchrabbittapp.com>.

publications that were already known to the authors but did not appear in the database or AI-assisted searches. In total, 66 relevant studies were identified and analysed. The corpus of studies is geographically diverse, encompassing global, regional, and multiregional perspectives, with no exclusions made based on geographical focus. All included studies are in English; however, no non-English publications were excluded on linguistic grounds—rather, no relevant non-English sources were identified during the search. Fig. 2 also presents the distribution of publication years and study types among the included literature.

2.2. Basic understanding, current practices and gaps of feasibility assessment

In a feasibility assessment, the specific aspects of practical implementation that represent barriers or enablers of a mitigation option or pathway are analysed [2]. Feasibility assessment has been an established method for multi-dimensional evaluation (MDE) of hindering and enabling conditions for sector-specific mitigation options, using scoring techniques introduced in the IPCC AR6 Report [2] since its introduction by SR1.5 [13]. The extent of feasibility increases when barriers are reduced and enablers are established.

Therefore, addressing the transformation barriers is crucial for feasibility assessments, as highlighted in recent studies. For example, Gailani et al. [14] reviewed the challenges of mitigation in nine major emitting industry subsectors, whereas Hasanbeigi et al. [15] detailed the obstacles to steel industry transformation, including infrastructure, water demand, regulations, and skills. Nacke et al. [16] underscored the importance of socio-political acceptance in coal phase-out feasibility assessments. Feasibility assessments require clarity on three aspects: the context in which scenarios are assessed, the indicators across multiple dimensions, and the evaluation methods used. The following sections outline these pillars as the foundation for a more integrated and practicable feasibility assessment compared to current modelling practices.

2.2.1. Contextual factors of feasibility

Feasibility is context dependent. This insight is widely recognised across recent literature, highlighting that what may be feasible in one setting may not be feasible in another due to differences in political, institutional, technological, and socio-cultural conditions [2,17–19]. Feasibility varies across regions, actors, time horizons, and scales of implementation [2,19]. For example, a technology that is institutionally and economically viable in a high-capacity country may not be implementable in a lower-capacity region. Studies have also emphasised the need to distinguish the contextual aspects “what?”, “when?”, “where?”, “how?” and “for whom?”, as each introduces additional complexity and influences the potential for implementation [2,17,18,20]. Despite this recurring recognition, many feasibility assessments remain focused on techno-economic dimensions, with broader contextual conditions—such as institutional capacity, socio-political dynamics, and local constraints—either simplified or overlooked [18,21]. Despite this consensus, current research often treats context as an implicitly defined background assumption rather than an explicitly defined analytical component [20]. The lack of explicit and operational guidance on how to define and incorporate context into feasibility assessments presents a critical gap. To ensure transparency, comparability, and relevance, context must be articulated more explicitly and systematically. This includes scenario development practices that reflect uncertainty and allow for context-sensitive comparison across multiple dimensions, as highlighted by Plazas-Niño et al. [22], who recommend constructing qualitative narratives and exploring multiple pathways to avoid oversimplification and to better represent real-world constraints.

2.2.2. Dimensions and indicators of feasibility

Feasibility is multidimensional and has to be assessed by considering relevant and suitable indicators from multiple dimensions. This understanding has been reflected in recent literature, especially in the context

of climate mitigation scenarios, where feasibility assessments increasingly go beyond technological and economic factors [23–25]. The IPCC's Special Report on Global Warming of 1.5 °C [13] and subsequent literature [2,19,26,27] propose a framework comprising six core dimensions: geophysical, technological, economic, institutional, socio-cultural, and environmental-ecological feasibility. These dimensions are understood to interact systemically, dynamically over time, and in spatially heterogeneous ways [13]. Although integrated models incorporate some of these dimensions [28,29], scientists have highlighted that real-world feasibility may diverge from stylised model representations. Moreover, empirical work [20,30] has emphasised the importance of sector-specific, context-aware indicator selection that captures relevant constraints and enablers. However, as Jewell and Cherp [31] argue, the current multidimensional frameworks face major methodological challenges. Chief among these are the unclear criteria for selecting appropriate indicators in specific contexts and the lack of a consistent approach for evaluating and aggregating them. Indicators are often treated as ad hoc or exhaustive, without sufficient justification or attention to context-specific relevance. As such, while the multidimensional structure offers a valuable conceptual scaffold, there is a lack of a practical, context-sensitive guideline that supports modellers in selecting, defining, and prioritising feasibility indicators in a transparent manner. This need is echoed in Plazas-Niño et al. [22], who highlight the importance of explicitly integrating social and behavioural dimensions—including public acceptance, political dynamics, and actor heterogeneity—into energy modelling frameworks to better capture real-world transition barriers.

2.2.3. Methods and practices in feasibility assessment

In practice, a common approach involves post-processing scenario outputs by comparing required capacities with historical precedents or projected availability. This includes indicators such as power generation capacities [32,33], technology deployment rates [34], and phase-out trajectories [35]. Feasibility constraints are also directly implemented in IAMs and ESMs, as seen in Iyer et al. [36], where institutional and behavioural factors were translated into mitigation delays.

Other studies combine historical analogies with modelling constraints, as in Napp et al. [37] and Muttitt et al. [38], who propose a six-step approach to systematically assess feasibility. However, soft constraints—such as political or social acceptability—remain difficult to quantify and incorporate [39]. identify political feasibility as a soft constraint, which can only be indirectly reflected in assumptions [40]. address this by adopting a cross-disciplinary methodology, combining modelling with empirically informed social science. Similarly, Neumann and Brown [41] use a modelling-to-generate-alternatives (MGA) approach to integrate social acceptance and other qualitative attributes into renewable energy systems design.

Cross-disciplinary methods are also gaining prominence. Choe et al. [42] propose integrating environmental lifecycle indicators into traditional energy systems metrics, highlighting the need to address regional ecological impacts. Other approaches include robust decision-making (RDM),⁵ multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM),⁶ and cross-impact

⁵ Robust decision making (RDM) deals with the performance of a concrete strategy compared to a variety of plausible alternatives based on the analysis of uncertainties, as described by Marchau et al. [45].

⁶ MCDM includes methods to support individuals or groups of decision makers to find the best solution for their specific problem among feasible alternatives, considering different quantitative and qualitative criteria explicitly to rank or classify the solutions, described by Cinelli et al. [64] and Thakkar [65].

Table 1

Comparison of existing literature on feasibility assessment methods and their assessment object, evaluation type, and stage of the scenario process. qn = quantitative aspects, ql = qualitative aspects. *Probabilistic evaluations are not shown by all references, but demonstrated by some. In this case, it is done by qualitative estimations, often supported by stakeholder involvements.

Framework/Method	Stages of data processing			Object of assessment				Type of evaluation			References
	Preprocessing	Processing	Postprocessing	Mitigation Options		Mitigation Pathways		Quantitative	Qualitative	Probabilistic	
				qn	ql	qn	ql				
Dimensions Framework Feasibility Spaces			●	●		●			●		[2,13,19,26–29] [17,31,51,52,57–60]
Model constraints		●		●				●			[28,33,34,36–38,41,54,61–63] [42,43,64–66]
MCDM model constraints using AHP		●				●		●			[42,43,64–66]
Using CIB for consistent scenarios	●			●	●	●	●	●			[44,67]
PESTEL Analysis				●	●			●	●		[68–72]
Model coupling		●				●	●	●	●		[40,42]
Analysis of historical analogies and comparison with study results	●		●			●		●			[32,35–38,43,51,57,58,61]
stakeholder involvement (e.g. workshops, surveys, ...)	●		●	●	●	●	●	●	●		[21,37,43,49,53,55,69,73]
Post calculation evaluation by specifically defining and analysing indicators			●	●		●		●			[18,23–25,34,46,74]
Post calculation evaluation with feasibility categories and/or descriptive evaluations			●	●	●	●	●	●	●*		[2,13–15,17,25,27,29,30,30,35,46–48,66,69–71,73,75]
Feasibility evaluation w/o scenario calculation			●	●	●			●	●		[13,21,40,47,48,66,70,76]

balance (CIB).⁷ For example, Gajdzik et al. [43] and Choe et al. [42] used the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to evaluate industrial transition scenarios, while Vögele et al. [44] applied CIB to assess expert-driven transformation pathways for the steel sector. Marchau et al. [45] link robustness and feasibility through scenario uncertainty management.

More novel approaches include qualitative assessments that classify feasibility in discrete categories—e.g. “trivial”, “challenging”, or “speculative” [35,46]. In-depth qualitative feasibility assessments based on stakeholder reflections or historical sector analyses have also proven valuable for identifying hard-to-abate sectors [47,48].

Empirical methods such as stakeholder interviews and surveys are another important source of feasibility insights [49]. These can be embedded in broader frameworks such as the widely adopted IPCC feasibility dimensions, which distinguish geophysical, technological, economic, institutional, socio-cultural and environmental-ecological dimensions [2,26,27]. Frameworks like the one developed by Gajdzik et al. [43] for metallurgical firms and Rogelj et al. [29] for scenario evaluations rely on this structure to enable multidimensional reflection.

Probabilistic and visual tools are also emerging. Threshold-based feasibility maps and causal-loop diagrams help visualise the feasibility landscape and causal structures [34,50]. Another promising method is the feasibility space approach, which situates mitigation options in a multi-dimensional space, comparing them with reference cases [51,52]. However, its application is limited by the availability of historical analogues and data richness.

Various other frameworks exist in the literature, such as the tripartite model of feasibility [18], meta-theoretical frameworks linking

⁷ Weimer-Jehle et al. [67] introduces CIB analysis as a tool designed to validate the internal consistency of storylines or qualitative scenarios and to identify the most consistent ones based on numerical judgments from experts or stakeholders regarding the state-dependent influences between key drivers.

techno-economic, socio-political, and behavioural aspects [39], and methods tailored for specific options such as carbon dioxide removal [27] or political feasibility [17]. While insightful, these are often highly specific and only appear once in the literature observed.

Finally, several studies highlight the growing importance of stakeholder involvement. Participatory modelling [53], backcasting processes [54], and co-production [55] can improve both the realism and acceptability of scenarios. Dioha et al. [56] argue that scenario research must develop new modelling structures, inclusive methods, and interdisciplinary approaches to better represent feasibility.

To synthesise these diverse contributions, we developed a comparative table (cf. Table 1) that classifies and evaluates the various feasibility assessment methods and frameworks discussed above. The table identifies the assessment object, evaluation type, and stage of the scenario process at which each method is applied. This systematic comparison reveals both areas of methodological complementarity and substantial fragmentation across approaches.

Some methods are strongly quantitative and model-integrated, while others are qualitative or externally applied. Some focus on specific feasibility dimensions (e.g. institutional or technological), others on holistic, multi-dimensional assessments. Certain approaches support scenario design (e.g. MGA), others are more suitable for post hoc analysis or stakeholder engagement. Many rely on historical analogies, expert judgement, or empirical data, but rarely do these converge into a unified procedure.

The study comparison shows inconsistent coverage of assessment targets and stages. Existing frameworks vary in what they assess—individual options vs. entire pathways—and when they assess it—during scenario generation, post-processing, or external evaluation. An overarching framework could help to coordinate these aspects and ensure that feasibility is assessed coherently across all stages.

2.2.4. Towards a comprehensive feasibility assessment

Despite a growing body of literature, feasibility assessment remains methodologically fragmented. From reviewing all the frameworks identified in the research literature considered, it becomes clear that the various methodological contributions are generally not combined into a coherent, structured process.

While theoretical principles for feasibility assessment have been outlined [31], there is limited operational support for modellers. Especially from a practitioner's perspective, the question remains: how can feasibility be systematically addressed in the modelling process to meet theoretical expectations?

From a practical perspective, especially relevant for modellers of ESMS, it remains insufficiently defined which model features and capacities are necessary to conduct robust feasibility assessments. This uncertainty is particularly acute in the context of industrial sector modelling, where unique characteristics—such as site-specific constraints, infrastructure interdependencies, long investment cycles, and sectoral policy environments—impose specific requirements on modelling frameworks [4]. Guidance is needed on how to adapt or extend ESMS to adequately reflect these feasibility-relevant features.

3. Materials and methods utilised in this study

This study addresses the research gaps identified in Sections 2.2.1 - 2.2.3 by developing a structured meta-framework for assessing feasibility in energy scenario studies. The framework builds on existing theoretical approaches, systematically links them through shared assessment dimensions and stages, and provides practical guidance for analysts and modellers. It aims to advance the consistency, transparency, and completeness of feasibility assessments in future scenario research.

Our approach combines insights from the extensive literature review (as outlined in Section 2) with the practical expertise of experienced energy systems modellers. The knowledge base generated through the literature review forms the analytical foundation of this study and underpins all proposed results. However, the goal of this work is not limited to theoretical synthesis; rather, it is to embed these findings into a methodologically sound and practically applicable framework proposed by modelling practitioners.

The team of authors includes experienced developers and users of seven international ESMS and IAMs (see Fig. 3). All of these models and associated modellers have recently taken up the challenge of integrating feasibility-related considerations into contributions to national decarbonisation pathways and NDC processes. These models consist of two industry-specific ESMS, namely, ITOM [77,104] and OECM [78,79], as well as five cross-sectoral ESMS and IAMs: PRIMES [100], SATIM-GE [80], AIM/Enduse-India (IIMA) [101], GCAM-USA [81], and China-MAPLE [102].

These models were not applied directly in the study. Instead, each was represented by a lead modeller with in-depth familiarity with the respective modelling framework. All representatives became part of the authorship team, ensuring continuous access to contextual and technical insights throughout the development process. This approach provided a unique opportunity to align the conceptual findings from the literature with practical experience and real-world modelling constraints.

At the outset of the research, each modeller was interviewed to determine the current state of feasibility integration in their respective models. These structured interviews were conducted with the author-modellers themselves, allowing for a shared understanding of current practices. Based on this foundation, exploratory discussions followed to identify how each model might, in the future, be better positioned to systematically integrate feasibility concerns. These discussions revealed which methods and practices are currently applied, what limitations exist, and what changes may be feasible or desirable in modelling practice going forward.

By synthesising evidence from both the literature and modelling practice, the study identified fundamental components essential for enabling feasibility assessments in relation to the context and content of a study and the model and assessment process used. For each component, we identified the research gaps of the current literature (see Section 2.2.1 - 2.2.3) and developed conceptual and systematic methods to address the gaps. The resulting elements were subsequently integrated with the theoretical discourse from Section 2 to construct a consolidated framework that reflects both conceptual rigour and practical relevance. Through multiple iterative rounds of internal review and co-author dialogue, the framework—and the associated concepts of context and content—were refined to ensure robustness and applicability. This collaborative and iterative process enabled the development of a

Fig. 3. Models and their regional distribution, which serve as sources for background knowledge and expertise from scientific ESMS modelling.

Fig. 4. The four fundamental elements and key questions for context definition to improve feasibility assessment within a model-based scenario study. The assigned numbers refer to respective paper sections.

methodological structure that bridges the gap between theory-based methods and modeller-oriented implementation.

The conceptual framework developed in this study was designed to be operationalizable, ensuring its practical relevance across diverse modelling contexts. Examples and recommendations are provided in the framework description to facilitate implementation. These examples were generalised to accommodate a wide range of potential applications and the diversity of existing modelling environments.

In a final step, we translated the framework into concrete implications for future energy systems modelling and identified possible challenges in applying the framework in practice. As far as possible, recommendations for future research are formulated.

4. Advancing model-based feasibility assessment: key findings and tools

The analysis of literature and modelling practice reveals four core elements that can improve feasibility assessments in model-based scenario studies (see Fig. 4). These are (Section 4.1): a clearly defined context, as feasibility is inherently context-specific (Section 4.2); a multidimensional set of feasibility concerns, captured through appropriate indicators (Section 4.3); a structured evaluation process that integrates these elements; and (Section 4.4) modelling improvements derived from requirements of context, indicators and evaluation.

4.1. Clarifying the assessment context: a structured 5W1H approach

The context defines the scope of an industry mitigation study and comprises information that comes from outside and is fixed by real constraints. The context information itself defines the current and target situations of the transformation and sets the boundary conditions for the study to assess feasibility. This is crucial, as feasibility is highly context-dependent, especially in the industry sector, which due to its heterogeneity encompasses a broad spectrum of potential contextual conditions (e.g. individual products, processes, companies, or subsectors).

The investigated literature highlights that feasibility can only be assessed effectively when the specific context is clearly defined [17,18,31].

However, we observe a lack of structured approaches to defining context more explicitly, both in the existing literature and within the NDC modelling practices of the experts involved in this study, which was observed in interviews and in-depth discussions about their previous context definitions. None of them reported having systematically and explicitly defined the context in previous scenario studies, and a shared need emerged for clearer guidance on what constitutes 'context' and how it could be structured.

To address this issue, this study provides an overview of the essential contextual information required for feasibility studies, which is depicted

schematically in Fig. 4. The essential context information is categorised into aspects of "Where?", "What?", "When?", "Who?", "How?", and "Why?" using the 5W1H-Method [82,83]. This method seamlessly connects to information from the literature and therefore seems to be a suitable choice for context definition.

The spatial component of the study is addressed by the question "Where?", which defines the region under investigation, ranging from global to individual plant scales, and determines the perspective of the study. The answer to the question "Why?" defines specific targets of mitigation efforts, such as reducing carbon emissions by a certain percentage or limiting global warming to a specific temperature increase. The target formulation depends on the spatial level of consideration, the "Where?", and can include different references and benchmarks (e.g. annual emissions, emission budgets, and energy use). Accordingly, the question "When?" outlines the time horizon for transformation and, thereby, the temporal component of the study.

The object of transformation is addressed by the question "What?" encompassing the industry subsectors, processes, and/or products under investigation. Existing mitigation options and thus potential solutions for transforming the object of transformation are described by the question "How?" typically involving technological alternatives, process efficiency enhancements, fuel and technology substitutions, and circular economic strategies in an industrial context. It is essential to transparently define the system boundaries of both the object of transformation and the mitigation options, clarifying which process steps are included and excluded. Valuable guidance can be provided by international classifications, such as the ISIC [84] or the Central Product Classification (CPC) [85], also applied by statistics such as the International Energy Agency (IEA) World Energy Balance [86]. In real-world studies, which often involve multiple current and future processes, each process must be carefully defined and bounded to ensure consistency, transparency, and accuracy.

The reflexive consideration of agency, a key feasibility principle [31], is integrated through the question "Who?", identifying the target group responsible for implementing necessary decisions and utilising the study's findings.

The 5W1H components of context definition are illustrated by an example definition of the study context in Table 2, motivated by the goal of enhancing NDCs in the steel industry. Each part of this example can be replaced and enhanced according to the specific conditions of the real-world case study.

Given the intricate relationships between contextual components, it is essential to consider context as a holistic entity and carefully assess the ripple effects of changes in individual components on other related elements. This comprehensive approach ensures that the context of the study remains coherent and consistent.

Table 2
Exemplary definition for the context of a study for the iron and steel industry.

Type of Context	Exemplary Context definition for an industry sector study utilising the model ...						
	ITOM	PRIMES	SATIM-GE	OECD	AIM/Enduse-India (IIMA)	China-MAPLE	GCAM-USA
Where?	EU-27 (with Member State representation)		South Africa	Australia	India	China	USA
Why?	Achieving net zero emissions according to NDCs and/or being Paris-compatible, e.g. "holding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels [...]" [103].						
What?	Decarbonisation of the steel production in Iron and Steel industry [ISIC Rev. 4 Group 241 and Class 2431]						
How?	Existing options are for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Replacement of current steel production processes using Blast Furnaces (BF) and Basic Oxygen Furnaces (BOF) by implementation of Hydrogen based Direct reduction of iron (H2 DRI) and subsequent steel production using Electric Arc Furnaces (EAF). ● Enhancement of current steel production processes using Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). For further options, see literature, e.g. [87]						
Who?	Each region's government						
When?	from today to 2050						

4.2. From indicator categories to clear definitions: building blocks for feasibility assessment

The choice of appropriate indicators is decisive in addressing the most relevant concerns in feasibility assessments. However, neither in the observed modelling practices considered in this study nor in the literature (cf. Section 2.2.2) the application of a structured approach for indicator selection and definition is seen, which leads to the conclusion that a methodological approach is needed to identify relevant concerns in a given context and to select and define appropriate indicators. Indicators are considered suitable when they are contextually relevant, significant to the target audience, and consistently defined to ensure comparability across studies.

Selecting relevant indicators is a critical yet challenging task for modellers, particularly given the time and budget constraints often associated with studies. Therefore, it is essential to utilise available resources to focus on the most relevant feasibility concerns. From the modeller's perspective, an exhaustive list of indicators, from which

study specific indicators can be selected, would be desirable. However, according to Ref. [31] such a list of specific indicators is not useful because it is not applicable to all cases owing to the variety of possible contexts and study. Instead, the selection and definition of indicators must be individualised, which poses two key challenges. First, it leads to a large number of case-specific indicators in the scientific community, making it difficult or impossible to reuse them in subsequent studies. Second, comparability between different studies is methodologically challenging, as the indicators are defined differently, and a standardised methodology for aggregating the indicators does not exist [31].

To address this issue, we introduce feasibility indicator categories designed to support modellers by providing clearly defined categories of potential feasibility concerns. These categories are broadly formulated to allow for individual customisation while maintaining clarity. They should enable researchers to use them in "retroductive identification of relevant concerns [...]" ([31]: p.10) and prevent them from "[...] abductive rationalisation of ad hoc indicators" ([31]: p.10). Therefore, they are intended to serve as input for initial considerations and

Fig. 5. Dimensions of feasibility and associated indicator categories to identify and define relevant indicators of feasibility.

discussions, ideally conducted in collaboration with the target audience. Furthermore, they can inform methodological prioritisation processes by employing techniques such as the MoSCoW method [88], pairwise comparisons, or surveys conducted with the target audience.

Although the dimensions framework [2] has been subject to valid criticism and limitations [31], it nonetheless provides a useful conceptual starting point for study design and scenario modelling. This strength is taken up by using the dimensions framework as a methodological entry point for defining categories of feasibility indicators across the six dimensions it introduces: technological, economic, institutional, geophysical, environmental, and socio-cultural feasibility. These categories are designed to be clearly distinguishable yet adaptable to specific use cases within each dimension. Notably, the dimensions introduced by Shukla et al. [2] also encompass the feasibility spheres described by Gajdzik et al. [43]. While Brutschin et al. [26] argue that the environmental dimension may reflect normative aspirations rather than practical constraints, we consider it relevant to feasibility assessments—particularly where issues such as particulate matter emissions or water consumption could pose implementation barriers in light of regulatory frameworks. Similarly, Förster et al. [27] replace the geophysical dimension with a “system utility” dimension, specifically tailored to carbon dioxide removal technologies. However, we retain the geophysical dimension due to its value in capturing physical and technical boundary conditions. In contrast, we chose not to include the system utility dimension, as we regard mitigation potential not as a primary implementation hurdle but as a strategic consideration. Furthermore, while the PESTEL framework [70] provides separate political and legal categories, we integrate these under a broader “institutional” dimension in our framework, while still ensuring that political and legal feasibility concerns are treated as distinct subcategories. For each dimension considered, we examined whether the corresponding indicators and subcategories could be incorporated into our proposed structure. The resulting feasibility dimensions and their associated indicator categories are presented in Fig. 5, with further details provided in Appendix A.

In a simplified manner, the team of authors went through this process of prioritising feasibility concerns with the feasibility indicator categories mentioned above to check the concrete operationalisation. In doing so, we encountered a central challenge early on, namely the different interpretations of individual indicator categories against the background of their respective contexts. To correctly prioritise an aspect of feasibility, each user must first interpret the aspect by themselves drawing on their individual background knowledge and experience. This leads to different interpretations and prioritisations, emphasising that an exhaustive list of indicators is not useful. Moreover, prioritising an entire category is not always easy, because it contains several individual aspects. For example, parts of a category should be prioritised, whereas the rest should be prioritised rather low.

However, this approach also presents a significant strength: by using indicator categories in a prioritisation process rather than single

indicators, participants are automatically forced into an exchange, bringing different interpretations to light. Although this may vary by global, national, or sub-sectoral perspective, the characterised indicator categories are applicable for all. Even if only parts of a category are relevant, the initiated discussion process helps identify them. Therefore, it is a valuable tool for identifying the most important aspects while creating a common understanding among team members, stakeholders, and modellers involved.

Modellers often operate under limited resources, including data limitations, which can complicate a full prioritisation process. This process is resource-intensive and requires the engagement of diverse stakeholders and the application of rigorous methods to minimise bias. Despite these challenges, we argue that even a simplified prioritisation process, one involving a small number of participants and potentially some degree of bias, can provide significant value. This approach enables the identification of relevant expansion potentials, thereby supporting the evolution of both the studied scenario and the associated information space. Our methodology, which employs indicator categories to address feasibility concerns and prioritises the most pertinent issues for a study’s target audience, offers a practical compromise. It balances the comprehensiveness of holistic approaches such as the Shukla et al. [2] method with the constraint of entirely excluding feasibility concerns. As a pragmatic recommendation, we suggest including as many additional feasibility concerns as resource permits, prioritised in descending order of relevance. Even considering a single additional aspect enhances the study’s value, contributing to better-informed decision-making.

Subsequently, a clear, transparent, and unambiguous **indicator definition** of all the selected indicators is crucial for enabling comparability and reproducibility. Only if the indicators are clearly and comprehensively defined can they be effectively compared to or reused in other studies. This reduces the diversity of the individual indicators. Therefore, it is essential to add a comprehensive description of the indicator name and its unit considering the defined context of the study according to the 5W1H-method (cf. Section 4.1). Ideally, this definition should be validated by or even co-created with the target audience to ensure consensus. For example, if employment effects are covered (see Fig. 6), it is necessary to precisely define the aspects that are included and excluded. In this case, employment effects can consider different age classes or different genders but can also be understood as gross or net employment effects.

When defining specific indicators, it can also be beneficial to draw upon existing research (cf. Section 2) or utilise collections of indicators, such as those provided by the IEA, especially the comprehensive handbook on energy efficiency indicators [89] or the indicators adopted in the IEA Greenhouse Gas R&D Programme [90]. Additionally, Obileke and Mukumba [91] provide a list of economic indicators with explanations on purpose and correct usage. By leveraging existing resources, researchers can ensure that their chosen indicators are guided by best practices and relevant expertise, thereby improving comparability.

Fig. 6. Indicator definition of “Employment Effects” as an example.

Fig. 7. Generalised approach for feasibility assessments in model-based scenario studies, where feasibility-relevant aspects can be considered iteratively and incrementally – the *Feasibility Loop*.

4.3. The Feasibility Loop: iterative integration of methods and knowledge

This section presents the *Feasibility Loop* (cf. Fig. 7), which is our proposed concept of a practical and comprehensive methodological framework for feasibility assessments in model-based studies. The process integrates the established context of a study and the selected indicators and provides appropriate methods to generate the necessary information to evaluate feasibility. A key element of this framework is the ESM, which can represent causal interdependencies within the energy system, providing internally consistent solutions [31] and enabling the exploration of diverse future scenarios by adjusting exogenous inputs and parameters [92].

The assessment process adopts an iterative approach, incrementally expanding the scope of feasibility considerations to refine the informational basis for informed discussion and evaluation. This contrasts with a holistic approach that seeks to analyse all relevant aspects simultaneously. Given the limitations of current models [31] and typically constrained resources, an incremental approach is more practical, integrating relevant aspects step-by-step.

The *Feasibility Loop* (Fig. 7) synthesises methodological insights from the literature and practical expertise from modellers within the team of authors into a comprehensive overview diagram, which is further

explained in the following sections. This visualization serves as a method toolbox, designed to assist modellers in navigating methodological complexity and choosing the appropriate methods for their use case. This enables them to categorise their practices, critically assess their suitability, and gain inspiration for further consideration.

The *Feasibility Loop* consists of five basic steps.

- 1 Current and target situations: Collect and define all relevant contextual information to describe the scope of the study (see Section 4.1).
- 2 Energy Systems Model: Translating the defined context and collecting information for feasibility assessment into a theoretical model structure through abstraction and mathematisation, creating a detailed representation of the system under investigation.
- 3 Theoretical model solution: Processing the model using numerical calculations to generate theoretical results.
- 4 Real results: The calculated results are interpreted in a real context by forming causal relationships from the model solutions and checking their consistency.
- 5 Evaluation and iteration: Check the validity of the results in the defined context using suitable feasibility evaluation methods and scrutinise the context, indicators, and results. For this purpose, the

perspectives of stakeholders and, if necessary, external experts should be integrated into a suitable workflow. If necessary, a new iterative step is initiated based on the proposed changes.

4.3.1. Understanding constraint types: the core logic of the Feasibility Loop

Feasibility assessment requires the generation of both quantitative and qualitative information relevant to the factors influencing feasibility. This, in turn, necessitates the use of methodological approaches tailored to the specific nature of each type of information. To illustrate this complexity and to structure the variety of available methods, the *Feasibility Loop* (cf. Fig. 7) introduces a distinction between hard and soft constraints. Furthermore, soft constraints are categorised into qualitative and quantitative types, allowing for a more nuanced approach to their assessment.

Hard constraints are defined as limitations that are dictated by the laws of nature. They are non-negotiable and universally valid, making them fundamentally different from soft constraints. Examples include physical limits such as minimum temperature thresholds for industrial processes, spatial limitations, physical resource potentials like solar or wind potentials, or absolute ore availability. These constraints cannot be overcome, regardless of technological or societal advancement. Because they are inherently non-debatable and immutable, it is essential that scenario developers ensure compliance with these physical laws from the outset—either exogenously or by implementing model constraints. Therefore, hard constraints usually do not serve as subject of stakeholder discussions—they serve instead as foundational boundaries that must not be exceeded.

In contrast, **soft constraints** are not grounded in the laws of nature but are instead contingent upon human systems, societal structures, institutional settings, and policy environments. As such, they are changeable over time and often subject to political or societal negotiation. Their flexible and dynamic nature makes soft constraints particularly relevant for long-term scenario analysis and a central subject of stakeholder dialogue. To enable a clearer assessment of these constraints, we further distinguish between quantitative and qualitative soft constraints.

Quantitative soft constraints refer to all aspects of feasibility that can be measured or estimated numerically, such as capital requirements, energy demand, availability of skilled labour, and material needs. Due to their quantifiable nature, these constraints can be integrated into ESMs to support feasibility assessments. They are often operationalised by filtering out infeasible solutions during model runs—for example, when the demand for resources, technologies, infrastructure, or energy exceeds what is estimated to be available. Technological readiness, for instance, can be modelled using Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), as shown by Capros et al. [93], to account for the phased availability of technologies over time. Constraints such as workforce shortages or bureaucratic hurdles—like lengthy permitting processes—can be translated into time delays, which affect the implementation timeline. These limitations can be implemented in models either through cost penalties that discourage early adoption or by exogenously defining scenario assumptions, such as caps on the speed of technology deployment. In both cases, addressing these constraints—e.g., by improving administrative efficiency or increasing labour availability—can shift the point in time at which a given solution becomes feasible. However, as these types of constraints are always based on assumptions and projections, they should be the subject of continuous stakeholder dialogue and structured reflection. The robustness and relevance of quantitative soft constraints can also be enhanced by coupling the ESM with complementary quantitative models from other disciplines. For instance, the ESM may generate a baseline scenario that includes all key system variables, which can then be supplemented with results from life cycle assessment (LCA), resource criticality analysis, or macroeconomic modelling. This interdisciplinary approach strengthens the plausibility of constraint assumptions and improves the quality of the overall

feasibility assessment.

Qualitative soft constraints, by contrast, refer to non-quantifiable factors that nonetheless significantly influence the feasibility of implementation. These include political, societal, and workforce acceptance; corporate culture; the existence of strategic goals (such as NDCs); the need for organisational restructuring; conflicts of interest; and unclear or inconsistent regulatory frameworks. While these constraints are, in principle, subject to change, their evolution tends to be discontinuous and difficult to forecast. As a result, they are typically assessed in the present and are not easily projected into future scenarios. Although they may not directly feed into modelling of detailed transformation pathways, they are essential for identifying key areas of action to enhance feasibility. Qualitative soft constraints can be effectively assessed through transdisciplinary methods such as stakeholder surveys, interviews, or expert workshops. Moreover, deeper insights into such constraints can be gained by linking ESM baseline scenarios to findings from qualitative studies, e.g. from social sciences. For example, while a model may quantitatively estimate job creation linked to a specific technology, qualitative differentiation of the associated skill requirements—shaped by educational systems, labour market dynamics, and broader social conditions—can only be captured through interdisciplinary integration. Preparing model outputs in a way that interfaces effectively with qualitative studies enables a more nuanced understanding of feasibility, such as examining the long-term availability of appropriately skilled labour across different social contexts.

Although quantitative modelling and the use of explicit constraints are widely applied in the models considered here, there is still a need for improvement in cooperative coupling with other models and studies. This requires a willingness to cooperate as well as a suitable platform and funding. Both are usually implemented through corresponding projects, highlighting the need for more transdisciplinary scientific projects to implement qualitative constraints.

After generating the required information for the feasibility assessment, the theoretical solutions must be translated into real results by establishing causal relationships. To achieve this, model results are placed in a real-world context by forming causal chains of events that either hinder or enable implementation, which include causal links between the technical potential of a mitigation option and the required initiatives and behavioural changes [18]. This enables causal reasoning in the subsequent feasibility evaluation, a crucial feasibility principle emphasised by Jewell and Cherp [31]. With causal reasoning, the evaluation of feasibility no longer refers only to a single event and its technical potential—for example, the implementation of an H2 DRI plant in steel production—but also to a chain of causal relationships between the single event and all associated parts of the economy. The modeller must ask himself the question “If event X occurs, how does it affect Y?” where Y can be, for example, part of the upstream and/or downstream value chain, regional economy, regional society, and so on. Forming causal chains seems extensive and requires methods such as CIB, causal loop diagrams [50] and the involvement of expert knowledge, but it creates consistency within the storyline of a scenario and is therefore essential for the real-world context.

4.3.2. Evaluating feasibility: interpreting constraints and their implications

The feasibility evaluation within the *Feasibility Loop* (Fig. 7) involves an MDE that compares the anticipated requirements with the available capacities for each indicator. For example, it may include comparing energy availability with energy demand, financial resources with projected costs, or spatial capacity with spatial requirements. Indicators act as barriers when required capacities exceed available capacities, thereby hindering their implementation. Conversely, when available capacities surpass requirements, the indicators become neutral or enabling factors that facilitate implementation. The magnitude of these gaps and whether barriers can be overcome form the basis of discussions. The information generated through the *Feasibility Loop* supports this critical discourse.

The involvement of stakeholders improves the accuracy of the model and the realism of the modelling assumptions, resulting in a greater impact at each iteration step made [53]. The utilised data and assumptions, as well as the limitations and uncertainties, are always debatable and should, therefore, be presented and discussed transparently. Discussing the modelling results with stakeholders offers valuable feedback and helps identify blind spots, while an iterative improvement process allows for ongoing dialogue and refinement of the model to enable informed decision-making [53]. To decide whether a further iteration should be carried out and which changes and additions appear useful for this run-through, MCDM methods can be helpful to collaboratively determine whether the generated path contains sufficient information for informed decision-making or whether additional iterations are necessary. Similarly, CIB methods can be useful for identifying and analysing the interdependencies between the investigated feasibility indicators, which should be investigated in an additional iteration. McGookin et al. [53], Hermwille et al. [94], and Righetti [95] provided practical guidelines for implementing effective stakeholder engagement at different stages of the *Feasibility Loop*.

Feasibility assessments applying the dimensions framework often utilise a scoring system to qualitatively evaluate whether an indicator has positive, negative, or mixed effects on the transformation [31]. Since feasibility is probabilistic [21], there is no “yes or no” answer to feasibility questions. Additionally, there is no universally valid evaluation scheme for all indicators, because each indicator has its own characteristic. Therefore, we do not recommend to use a qualitative scoring system as a general rule. Rather, we recommend considering how to evaluate these indicators when defining it. For example, quantitative evaluations using threshold values, qualitative evaluations using scoring, and probabilistic evaluations using reference cases and feasibility spaces can be considered. The feasibility space [31] proves to be a valuable tool here as it enables and visualises links between knowledge from theory and practice. This visually situates the calculated results within the context of the relevant reference cases, enabling the attachment of the probability estimates to the calculated scenarios. The challenge of collecting numerous reference cases to span a feasibility space can be addressed pragmatically. This involves comparing the calculated results with a small but carefully selected set of reference cases, thereby placing the results into a real-world context [31].

The defined context (Section 4.1) must be considered in the feasibility evaluation because it can lead to different results. For instance, whether a decrease or increase in employment is considered an enabler or barrier depends on the country and its circumstances. In countries where unemployment is already high, such as South Africa [96], or where population growth is expected, such as India, a decrease in employment is not sustainable and may lead to immediate limitations in implementation. In regions with declining population growth and acceptable low unemployment rates, on the other hand, a decline in employment demand can even be evaluated as an enabler. This is a part of the *Feasibility Loop*, in which the quantitative and qualitative constraints become evaluable for the modeller by placing them in their defined context and examining them from multiple (stakeholder) perspectives.

When evaluating indicators, it should be noted that some are mutually dependent, as in the case of human capabilities and employment effects. This means that individual indicators have limited informative value and gain impact when other indicators are added. The argument that an option creates jobs is not necessarily a good one, as the question of what kind of jobs are created needs to be clarified, and whether reskilling or even relocating workers is necessary. If there is already a shortage of skilled labour, it may not be feasible to create additional jobs in this field in the short term. The iterative and incremental approach of the *Feasibility Loop* (cf. Fig. 7) is advantageous, as the employment effects are first modelled and evaluated, and the model is then expanded with relevant skill requirements to increase its informative value. For instance, Fragkos and Paroussos [97] presented a

method for modelling this issue.

Should indicators that exert an indirect influence on the industry, such as ecotoxicity, be included, this necessitates the incorporation of a further mechanism that generates a direct influence. Therefore, a regulatory measure that translates ecotoxicity into industry specifications based on threshold values is required. Only then can the feasibility of the implementation be assessed. For the modeller, this necessitates an examination of the mechanisms of action that transform an indirect influence into a direct influence, enabling their incorporation into the causal chain and the assessment of the indirect influence.

The current modelling practices identified and applied by the authors were assessed as follows with regard to feasibility evaluation.

- Conditions relevant to feasibility have already been included in the validations in some cases but usually only implicitly.
- The involvement of stakeholders is desired and is already being implemented in some cases, but often only to validate results. The joint project work of the authors showed that the implementation of best-practice approaches requires considerable effort, and resources must be allocated accordingly.
- In particular, the involvement of stakeholders at the beginning of a study on the definition of context and indicators is rarely implemented. However, there is scope for further improvement.

4.4. Towards better models: developing and adapting models for feasibility assessments

The primary purpose of modelling is to abstractly represent the given context in a realistic manner and capture all the necessary systemic relationships to calculate the desired contents of the investigation. This makes it an essential tool within the *Feasibility Loop* (cf. Fig. 7). The structure and design of a model are heavily dependent on the context and indicators. In particular, when representing the industry sector, the relevant value chains must be modelled along with the adjacent elements of the overall system that influence the industry sector. To achieve this, the model should have four essential properties, which are explained in detail below.

To develop, implement, and run a model representing an abstract version of the real-world system under consideration within the defined context, a suitable **accounting framework** is essential, offering a structured development environment. This framework solves the defined equation system and mathematically balances the input and output commodities and the systemic dependencies of the modelled processes for each specified time step to finally reach the target year. It is advantageous to implement algorithms that filter infeasible solutions during the calculation. The authors' own expertise in modelling energy systems is based on different proprietary or available open-source frameworks that use different approaches (optimisation versus simulation) to solve the system of equations. The approach to represent an economy differs between partial equilibrium models, which focus on specific aspects of a particular region's economy, and general equilibrium models, which consider the entire economy.

The quantitative accounting of feasibility-relevant aspects requires high **technological granularity** realised through a **bottom-up modelling approach**. In the industrial sector, there is a strong dependency on the implementability of individual technologies and factors, such as technological readiness and technical restrictions, for the integration of alternative options and fuels. Therefore, it is essential to represent the industry sector and its dependencies in sufficient detail to enable the evaluation and discussion of feasibility. To represent these dependencies correctly, individual technologies are assigned specific parameters for the modelling process, such as specific energy requirements, material inputs, costs, or TRLs. The results of these calculations can be aggregated from a granular level (e.g. individual production lines) to higher levels (e.g. entire industrial sectors or the entire system). In the authors' current practice, technology-rich bottom-

up approaches are used in most cases. In IAMs and economic equilibrium models, technologies and sectors are often only roughly represented. In many ESMs, on the other hand, a variety of individual technologies and subsectors are considered. The models are usually limited to techno-economic parameters but are mostly well suited for supplementation by further assessment parameters.

The **spatial resolution** of a model must reflect the context and selected indicators as it critically affects the accuracy of statements about the system under investigation. In the industrial sector, the required level of granularity varies widely from global to individual industrial plants, depending on the context and content of the study. For instance, future access to the infrastructure of H₂ or CO₂ varies across sites at the subnational level and may not be addressed appropriately at the national level. This can be considered directly by modelling individual sites or indirectly by modelling aggregated categories of sites with different rates of likelihood of access to infrastructure, which is planned to be demonstrated, for instance, in the TRANSCIENCE project [98]. In both cases, plant-scale data were required. However, a spatial resolution that is too coarse or too fine can lead to misleading and unrealistic results by excessively expanding or unintentionally restricting choices, thereby limiting the usefulness of the model. The models considered in this study have different spatial granularities, at least at the country level. In some cases, several countries or subnational regions (states or provinces) have been modelled. Detailed country models can also include the spatial allocation of individual facilities in primary industries.

The effective implementation of changes to enhance model accuracy requires a high **degree of adaptability** in the modelling process of the *Feasibility Loop* (cf. Fig. 7). It would be desirable if additional indicators, a finer spatial resolution or a different context could be taken into account. An adaptable model enables efficient cycling between theoretical information generation and practical feedback, based on information evaluation. It allows for the direct involvement of stakeholders and the incorporation of external expert knowledge and enhances the model's relevance and accuracy. Notably, adaptability encompasses not only changes in context and study content but also necessitates synchronisation (e.g. checking consistency), and in some cases, perhaps coupling, with relevant supplementary studies and models, as evident from the presented process. In current practice, the models used have undergone several improvement processes that have led to extensions of the model structures. Constraint modelling was performed by adjusting the assumptions and cost-potential curves. The adaptability of this monetisation of aspects is limited. All models have already been applied to project-specific stakeholder processes and have already been used in combination with other models. This experience should be used synergistically in the future to establish further links.

Based on these considerations and reflections on current modelling practices, the following recommendations for successful modelling in the context of the overall *Feasibility Loop* can be derived.

- Starting the considerations with a concrete real-world application in collaboration with stakeholders and experts. Define your context precisely and build on it.
- Explore the aspects of feasibility that are relevant in your context. Focus on the aspects that are most important and implementable in *Feasibility Loop* practices by either modelling it directly or covering it using additional methods and studies. Thrive for objective feedback in each iteration cycle.

5. Discussion: limitations and scope for future research

This study examines, how the feasibility assessment of GHG mitigation options in the industrial sector through model-based scenario studies can be improved. By providing a structured and incremental approach, the framework supports practitioners in systematically identifying, evaluating, and integrating feasibility constraints into energy

systems modelling. Despite its potential, the framework faces several important limitations that must be acknowledged and addressed through future research and practical testing.

A key limitation lies in the availability and accessibility of data, particularly in the industrial sector. The feasibility assessment relies on diverse indicators—both qualitative and quantitative—many of which are not readily available, standardised, or harmonised across modelling contexts [22]. Industrial data are often fragmented, confidential, or vary significantly across subsectors and individual facilities, hindering comparability and consistency. This poses particular challenges not only for assessing feasibility but for industrial modelling more broadly. The initial conditions of an energy system—strongly shaped by the quality of input data—can create significant inertia in model outcomes, underscoring the need for robust and reliable data from the outset [22]. While recently published datasets, such as Teske et al. [99], offer a promising foundation by providing detailed emissions data and carbon budgets for EU-27 industries, broader, more standardised, and regularly updated data efforts are needed. Establishing dedicated feasibility-related datasets—aligned with FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)—would significantly improve the reliability and scalability of the framework across diverse industrial and national contexts.

Another limitation concerns the resource intensity of the proposed approach. Conducting a comprehensive feasibility assessment that iteratively engages stakeholders and integrates various types of data is both time- and resource-consuming. In practice, the implementation of all framework components may not always be feasible. For this reason, we explicitly recommend that practitioners treat the Feasibility Loop not as a rigid protocol but as a flexible, modular toolbox. Individual steps and methods can be adapted or selectively applied depending on project-specific objectives, available expertise, and resource constraints. Future research should explore how different configurations of the framework perform under varying boundary conditions, and which elements provide the greatest added value when resources are limited.

A further challenge relates to the composition of the expert group involved in developing the framework. All interviewees were also co-authors of this paper. While this enabled deep technical discussions, direct access to model-specific insights, and a high level of commitment to a joint framework design, it may also have introduced confirmation bias or led to a relatively uniform perspective on current modelling practices. To enhance robustness, generalisability, and critical reflection, future research should involve a broader and more diverse set of modelling experts—including external practitioners not directly involved in the framework's development. Independent case applications and critical stakeholder feedback will be crucial in identifying limitations, improving usability, and increasing relevance for different industrial contexts.

Moreover, as a conceptual framework, its real-world applicability and operational feasibility remain largely untested. Its successful implementation depends on how well the proposed elements can be embedded in diverse modelling workflows, institutional processes, and sectoral conditions. The integration of qualitative soft constraints—such as social acceptance or political stability—poses a particular methodological challenge, as these are not easily translated into numerical model inputs. More work is needed to identify and establish robust interfaces between qualitative and quantitative approaches, including interdisciplinary methods that link ESMs with social sciences, political analysis, or behavioural research.

To advance the research agenda and address the limitations identified above, we recommend the following directions for future work.

- Pilot applications and real-world case studies across different industrial subsectors and modelling contexts to evaluate the operational feasibility, identify context-specific challenges, and generate empirical evidence for refining the framework.

- Cross-disciplinary integration, particularly with social and political sciences, to capture and operationalise qualitative soft constraints, and to improve the design of feasibility indicators that reflect institutional, social, and behavioural dynamics.
- Development of digital tools and support instruments (e.g. templates, indicator libraries, or modular software components) to assist practitioners in applying the framework effectively, especially under time or resource constraints.
- Enhanced stakeholder engagement strategies, including practical guidance on how and when to involve stakeholders to maximise relevance, prioritise key feasibility constraints, and align study objectives with real-world decision-making.
- Transparent documentation of framework use cases, supported by a shared repository of practical experiences, methodological adaptations, and lessons learned to support learning across the modelling community.
- Establishment of feasibility-related datasets and indicator catalogues, supported by open data initiatives and guided by FAIR principles, to enhance comparability, transparency, and robustness in future feasibility assessments.

Despite the challenges in implementation such a framework offers a promising structure for making feasibility more tangible and operational in model-based scenario studies. By addressing its current limitations and expanding its empirical foundation, the framework has the potential to significantly improve the policy relevance and real-world applicability of ESMs—contributing to more actionable and grounded decarbonisation strategies for the industrial sector. We explicitly welcome critical feedback and diverse practical experiences to support its continued refinement.

6. Conclusions

This study examines various aspects of the feasibility of mitigation options and pathways and proposes a conceptual framework for systematically integrating feasibility assessments into model-based studies, particularly on the industrial sector.

6.1. Theoretical implications

The concept advances the theoretical understanding of feasibility by distinguishing between hard constraints, quantitative soft constraints, and qualitative soft constraints, and by introducing structured indicator categories as a foundation for context-specific assessments. The framework complements techno-economic modelling by embedding trans-disciplinary and iterative elements that address real-world implementability. It also contributes to methodological literature, e.g. by applying the 5W1H method to guide context definition and by highlighting key modelling requirements such as granularity and adaptability. By offering a modular, adaptable structure, the framework supports a deeper theoretical discourse on feasibility in energy systems modelling and opens new directions for interdisciplinary research. While the focus of this study is conceptual, the theoretical contributions are grounded in an extensive and systematic literature analysis covering a broad range of recent academic publications, from which key patterns and gaps in current modelling practices were derived and categorised.

6.2. Practical implications

From a practical perspective, the framework offers ESM practitioners a structured yet flexible approach to assess the feasibility of mitigation pathways and options. It serves as a toolbox that can be tailored to the available resources and project needs, rather than as a rigid process. Pre-defined indicator categories and guidance on stakeholder engagement help prioritise feasibility-relevant aspects early in the modelling process. Despite its conceptual maturity, real-world applications are still limited.

Future work should focus on operationalising the framework in diverse industrial settings, building dedicated feasibility-related datasets, and refining stakeholder interaction formats. By doing so, the framework can help make modelling more policy-relevant and implementation-oriented—supporting more grounded, credible, and actionable transformation pathways in the context of industrial decarbonisation. While this article does not yet include a full empirical application of the framework, its structure and content have been informed by in-depth exchanges with modelling practitioners. Future work will be needed to demonstrate its operational value through real-world case studies and implementation exercises.

CRedit authorship and contribution statement

Robin König: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization, Writing – Review & Editing. Thomas Pregger: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision. Stefan Kronshage: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Project administration. Patrick Jochem: Supervision, Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing. Bryce McCall: Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing. Georg Holtz: Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing. Saritha Sudharmma Vishwanathan: Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing. Panagiotis Fragkos: Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing. Teng Fei: Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing. Steven J. Smith: Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing. Sven Teske: Content Discussion, Writing – Review & Editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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